

A Framework at the Economic Growth Nexus, E-Government Portals: “Would It Help?”

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Abstract : This paper presents a model-derived framework to explain the existing relationship between the eGovernment domain and the Economic Growth domain. The aim is to provide a strategic framework that can support decision-makers when promoting digital transformation. The existing empirical literature shows that aspects of this relationship can be realized through the competitiveness index as a strategic mediator. The Global Competitiveness Index parameters are used for matching indicators from both domains. In this work, the composite indexes of the eGovernment Development Index (EGDI) are studied in the context of selected parameters for measuring the Economic Growth.

The population for the statistical analysis is done on all state members of the UN eGov used in the biannual eGovernment survey. It presents a genuine econometric model where results are pulled out from cross-sectional data analysis for 193 observations over the year 2018. The GDP per capita is selected as the output function, whereas the right-hand side is selected parameters for three main factors; Trade, Labor, and Technology. Trade predictors are selected to be Inflation –as a GDP deflator - FDI, number of days to start a business, and Import, and Export. As for Labor, predictors are selected to be HCI -Infant Mortality, Adult Literacy, and School enrollment for Tertiary education. Whereas for Technology predictors are selected to be Fixed and Mobile (Cellular) Telephone Subscribers, Fixed and Wireless BroadBand subscribers, Internet users, EGDI, eParticipation.

Findings agree with the literature and the model proves the positive influence of eGov on economic growth. The contribution of this research work is bi-fold. Firstly, the new fitness function provides quantifiable evidence linking the eGovernment and economic growth via two basic factors; Technology and Trade. Secondly, the exploration of the regression analysis provided a deeper understanding of the magnitude of influence occurring within these explanatory factors. It is found that the economic parameter “Number of days to start a business” inversely proportional with and relevant to the “Technology factor” rather than the “Trade factor” as previously perceived in the literature. In addition, the investigation came over the bonds between “Online Services Index” and “eParticipation index”. In addition, the inter-relation between HCI calculated by the World Bank established to be more comprehensive as it included the HCI-UN together with the social parameters. Thus, the framework is derived from economic theories and models found relevant from the literature and are adding to the body of knowledge on both levels, the academic and the practice.

IndexTerms - Economic Growth, EGDI, E-Government, Framework, GDP, Global Competitiveness Index.

I. INTRODUCTION

Digital transformation is everywhere, especially after the spread of COVID-19 pandemic. Many countries around the world are adopting this transformation more than before the critical situation that hit the world early 2020. This transformation mandates more reliance on ICT systems and services. The demand for digital economy, digital government, digital education, and digital inclusion ...etc, are increasing. Decision makers are forced to foresee the strategic opportunities laying ahead.

Likewise, the digital economy is a newly emerging form of economy that is gaining momentum from the recent digital era. This new form of economy is based on intellectual resources, Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), science-intensive industries, and modern services that create a qualitatively new technological level to the entire national economy. In return, it is creating a safe environment for investment and new business opportunities. It is perceived to promote economic growth and to accelerate productivity.

Simultaneously, governments are undergoing reformation, as much as the economies, caused by modern information technologies. Governments around the world are experiencing digital transformation as those who are still delivering information and services to stakeholders in the traditional format are now becoming history. In some countries, governments are simply digitizing their processes; others are taking bold paradigm shift in their path towards digital transformation. It is believed that the innovation coming along with available electronic services are increasingly affecting the national competitiveness levels. Governments are evolving too by undergoing different levels of transformation with their processes and it is affecting their national competitiveness levels.

International organizations such as the UN-Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) introduced a definition for governments that are embracing Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) to deliver their services with the name “Electronic Government” (e-Gov). It is expected that eGov portals will improve the quality of

services delivered to citizens. Furthermore, it is perceived that any enhancements in competitiveness can be related to the uplift of the economy accordingly. The literature discussing eGovernment development has categorized the stakeholders of the portals to four main types. Services and systems serving Citizens (G2C), Businesses (G2B), interoperability between governmental bodies (G2G), and internal relations within its employees (G2E). As it can be seen from the definitions stated in figure (1), the main target groups of e-government initiatives delivery models include four main blocks: citizens, businesses, governments, and employees.

E-government initiatives delivery models

Figure 1. Source created by authors

It is worth mentioning, Majeed et al. (2019) stated that “Although, the theoretical literature discusses the positive impacts of e-government on economic success of a country but empirical studies on e-government are still missing”. There is a need to analyze the contribution of e-government on economic growth. This study contributes to the existing literature and quantifies the relationship between eGov portals and economic growth using the UN eGov survey covered in the 2018 with their corresponding economic parameters.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The digital transformation of governments mandates intense utilization of the available ICT. It provides the enabling technologies needed for the digital economy. Governmental portals can attain the digital transformation by supporting software applications and developing systems rooted in their operations. In order to boost their economy’s competitiveness, policy makers are perceiving potential in the development of their electronic governmental portals.

Many scholars acknowledged that E-government and ICT systems have the potential to add value to public services within countries of different economic status. Therefore, it is agreed that e-Gov portals are increasingly affecting the competitiveness levels of the country. Nevertheless, European Commission (2006) has noted that countries with high ranked public sector eGov portals tend to top the economic performance and competitiveness scoreboards. This can explain why the European Commission has launched an economic analysis that confirms the link between countries’ competitiveness and the quality of public administration. Stating that “...in the global economy better government is a competitive must.” (European Commission, 2006:3).

Similarly, the recent UN eGov portals survey for the year 2020 provides evidence for the same opinion. Data collected for GDP per Capita, using the UN survey for eGov portals of the year 2020, supports the same idea that claims economies are high for countries on top of the list of the EGDI. It is evident from graph (1) that some economies experience sustained economic growth while others do not. Recent research has been revolving around this quest, trying to understand the link between sources of growth from within technological indicators. Researchers in both domains, the eGov and the economic growth, have been investigating the topic lately.

The eGov development index in relative to economic status of countries

Graph 1. Source: 2020 United Nations E-Government Survey

II.1. EGOV BACKGROUND AND ICT

Governments around the world are utilizing the ICT systems and services in the public sector administration and planning Von-Haldenwang, (2004). The electronic services facilitate processes between governments and markets through their online websites. Governmental websites are supporting the digital economy in many ways. Their impact goes beyond merely increasing outlets of services, or promoting trade, or even leveraging the human capital. E-Government websites are the outcome production of ICT systems and services to stakeholders. Hence, the term e-Gov stems from the fact that governments are using the Internet and the underling technologies of ICT to develop systems for delivering an informative and useful operational websites. These interactive websites that are backed up with functionalities and systems are called: “Portals”. Graph (3) displays the history of ICT usage by individuals around the world.

Graph 2. Source ITU World Telecommunication/ICT indicators database. 1

The e-Gov portals act primarily as a “one stop” website that helps in delivering services and supports various running processes. These portals are expected to deliver services and communicate information to all its stakeholders. Scholars have identified e-Government to have possible “economic growth” progress. The definition of the term “Gross Domestic Product (GDP)” can be used to represent the growth and is estimated by “... the total monetary or market value of all the finished goods and services produced within a country's borders in a specific time period” (Chappelow, 2019). Thus, when aligning ICT technologies with the development of e-Gov portals, it can achieve acceptable economic growth.

The literature is clearly expressing the positive impact on GDP when related to investments in ICT infrastructure. Koutroumpis (2009) puts emphasis on the role of ICT to facilitate communications within different stakeholders and on how it can result in actually cost reduction and better country growth. Similarly, Mahyideen et al. (2012) discusses how ICT can result in an increase in productivity of labor and accordingly affect the economic growth of the country. In the same direction, Quah (2002) agrees on the fact that ICT can improve labor skills, affect education, facilitate Trade, increase integration, and enhance citizen’s participation.

The available studies in the literature that explore the impact of technology together with e-Government on growth are driven with focus on telecommunication infrastructure (IT) – or ICT- as the main base for a prosperous digital economy. Keeping in mind that these studies give examples drawn are experienced seldom on developed countries. Later, empirical evidences are then reflected on developing/under development economies. Recent sample of the developed countries with high reliance on ICT technologies is presented in graph (2). It displays the data presented in the last couple of reports issued by the UN for EGDI. It is clear that most of these countries are above 0.9 index value.

Summary of eGovernment development index across last couple of reports

Graph 3. Source: 2020 United Nations E-Government Survey. Graph created by author

Although ICT might be represented by many proxies such as Individuals using the Internet, FBB, FTS, or MTS, yet in most of the studies they used only one proxy for ICT. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that few research efforts

¹ <http://www.itu.int/en/ITU-D/Statistics/Pages/definitions/regions.aspx.html>

have properly studied the impact of eGov portal that is reflected in utilizing ICT technologies in order to affect the economic growth.

II.2. E-GOVERNMENT AND ITS ECONOMIC GROWTH NEXUS

E-Gov portals provide time effective and cost reduction that benefit different stakeholders; citizens, businesses, and administrations. In their study, Krishnan et al. (2013) proved that E-Gov could influence the economic growth of countries. In a similar study, Majeed and Malik (2016) provided evidence that E-Gov has positive links between both growth and Trade. Investigation of determinants of economic growth is considered the most active research area. Starting with exogenous growth models (Solow, 1957) to the endogenous growth models where growth is driven by the technological changes (Romer, 1990). On the other hand, Niebel (2018) study has concluded that developing countries might not benefit from ICT as much as developed countries. He discusses the cause to be due to ignoring the role of eGov portals when defining economic growth. Nevertheless, he approves the existence of a relationship between eGov and economic growth. In the same direction, the table (1) below displays the latest UN survey results (2020). The developed/developing country classifications are based on the UN for the years 2001-2019 can be presented in table (1).

eGovernment related to economic status

Levels of Income	EGDI	Online Service Index	Telecommunications Infrastructure Index	Human Capital Index
High income	0.8195	0.7663	0.8301	0.862
Upper middle income	0.6204	0.5515	0.5618	0.7478
Lower middle income	0.4932	0.4864	0.4036	0.5895
Low income	0.3021	0.3112	0.1984	0.3967

Table 1. Source United Nations E-Government Survey - 2020

This study presents analysis for countries with all types of economic status to study their respective e-Gov portals. In order to answer the main research question, “**How can e-Gov portals strategically boost the economic growth of countries?**” We have developed these main hypotheses:

H₀: Development of e-Government portals cannot affect economic growth of countries.

H₁: Development of e-Government portals can strategically affect economic growth of countries.

III. ECONOMETRIC MODEL

This research work aims to derive the model starting from Mankiw et al. (1992) empirical model that states:

$$y = f(A, k, n, h)$$

where y refers to the GDP per capita, A denotes the state of *Information Technology*, k represents *Trade*, n refers to the labor force and h is human capital. In our model, the labor force and human capital are combined in a *Social* factor. Therefore, it is considered a wider measurement for social progress.

$$y = f(A|K, S) \quad (1)$$

We also consider the *Technology* as the combination of ICT of the countries together with the variables of e-Gov and its underlying ICT systems and services. It is important to explain the GDP per capita in terms of *Information Technology (IT)*, *Trade* and *Social* factors. Hence, the equation 1 can be rewritten as equation 2.

$$f(y) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 A + \beta_2 K + \beta_3 S \quad (2)$$

$$f\left(\frac{GDP}{Capita}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1(ICT, eGovernment) + \beta_2(Trade) + \beta_3(Social) \quad (3)$$

The ICT has five main components, which are FTS¹, FBB², Internet users³, MTS⁴, MBB⁵. since these measures are highly correlated, their simultaneous estimations may have multi-collinearity issues. Consequently, this study estimate separate effect of each indicator of ICT. By substituting in equation (3), we get equation (3.1):

$$f(GDP/Capita) = \beta_0 + \beta_1(FTS, FBB, Internet, MTS, MBB, eGovernment) + \beta_2(Trade) + \beta_3(Social) \quad (3.1)$$

¹ Fixed Telephone Subscriptions (per 100 people)

² Fixed Broad Band subscriptions (per 100 people)

³ Individuals using the Internet (% of population)

⁴ Mobile Telephone Subscription (per 100 people)

⁵ Mobile (wireless) Broad Band subscriptions (per 100 people)

For the purpose of this study, the *Trade* factor includes selected variables, which are Inflation¹, FDI², and Number of Days to start a business, Imports³, and Exports⁴. Furthermore, the *Social* factor is the Human Capital Index HCI. Thus, equation (3) can be expanded to equation (3.2):

$$f(GDP/Capita) = \beta_0 + \beta_1(FTS, FBB, Internet, MTS, MBB, eGovernment) + \beta_2(Inflation, FDI, Days, Import, Export) + \beta_3(HCI) \tag{3.2}$$

This study selected variables to represent the labor and human capital measurements in the HCI. These variables are: Infant⁵ Mortality rate, Tertiary⁶ school education enrollment, and Adult⁷ literacy. By substituting in equation (3.2), we get:

$$f\left(\frac{GDP}{Capita}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1(FTS, FBB, Internet, MTS, MBB, eGovernment) + \beta_2(Inflation, FDI, Days, Import, Export) + \beta_3(Infa + SchEnr + Lit) \tag{3.3}$$

The UN measures the eGov Development index (EGDI) is based on the three indices TII, OSI, and HCI. The eGovernment progress is exemplified with EGDI together with the e-Participation index. The eParticipation index reflects the usage of the services provided online as a separate indicator. Since the model has another HCI variable, then the Human Capital Index will be called: HCI_{UN}. By substituting in equation (3.3), we get:

$$EGDI = \begin{cases} TII \\ OSI \\ HCI_{UN} \end{cases} \tag{4}$$

For purpose of a more reliable model, the study conducted analysis substituting the EGDI using its composite indices. Since all coefficients are estimated to be positive and significant, we reach the final model to be:

$$f\left(\frac{GDP}{Capita}\right) = \beta_0 + (\beta_1FTS + \beta_2FBB + \beta_3Intenet + \beta_4MTS + \beta_5MBB + \beta_6ePart + \beta_7TII + \beta_8OSI + \beta_9HCI_{UN}) + (\beta_{10}Inflation + \beta_{11}FDI + \beta_{12}Days + \beta_{13}Import + \beta_{14}Export) + (\beta_{15}Infa + \beta_{16}SchEnr + \beta_{17}Lit) \tag{5}$$

Equation (5) is the accepted profound model with the initial 17 independent variables to be considered for further statistical analysis.

IV. THE THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

In this paper, we are proposing a new framework to understand the nexus between eGov portals and growth. It is meant to be a tool decision makers can utilize to foster the competitiveness of their countries in the digital era. Our empirical framework, shown in figure (2), is proposing adjustments to the model presented by Hoa (2016). In order to draw emphases on the economic role of eGov portals, the Competitiveness pillars are chosen to be the strategic medium aligned with the goal of individual countries.

A preliminary diagram for the theoretical framework

Figure 2. Source: created by authors

¹ Inflation, GDP deflator (annual %)
² Foreign Direct Investment
³ Imports of goods and services (current US\$)
⁴ Exports of goods and services (current US\$)
⁵ Probability of survival under 5
⁶ School enrollment, tertiary (% gross)
⁷ Literacy rate, adult total (% of people ages 15 and above)

V. THE DATA AND RESEARCH METHOD

This section explains the sources from which data was extracted for the selected variables of the 193 countries as per year 2018. A list of the variables can be found in Appendix A with different sources.

V.1. DATA SOURCES

Data used in this study is extracted from multiple relevant sources as of the year 2018. Sample of such are: World Bank, International Monetary Fund, Balance of Payments Statistics Yearbook and data files, World Bank national accounts data, and the OECD National Accounts data files.

To study the hypothesis in this research, we explored the contextual nexus between various indicators of eGov portals, Competitiveness index, and economic growth parameters for all countries covered in the survey. We mainly focused on the relevant competitiveness pillars as a key player in the strategic development of eGov portals.

V.2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND DATA DESCRIPTION

The diversity of sources of the collected data postured many challenges. Different sources have different format, different naming conventions, ultimately different values, and even the availability in some cases. Other efforts are confronted with the difference in the naming conventions of countries in these different sources. Thus, the UN naming convention was adopted. Accordingly, all other sources underwent a rectification process to match and comply. In addition, all missing data for any of the independent variables resulted in deleting the whole record of the country. To overcome discrepancies in terms of redundancy or replicated data gathered from multiple sources for the same variable, the most recent values were assumed best relevant.

The format of the data values are not homogenous, some have unit values such as \$US, others are numeric, percentage, per population or percentage of population, and some are indexed. Variables are standardized to be from Zero to One (0-1). The dependent variable for measuring the economic growth is selected to be the real GDP per capita measured in current \$US.

V.3. DATA ANALYSIS

The GDP values are expected to be of better significance when related to population. The natural logarithm of real GDP per capita is used. It is used to view preliminary relationships between the GDP per capita and other variables. The correlation analysis done on all listed 17 variables in equation (5) using professional statistical software¹. The results indicated preliminary modifications to some variables, namely: Inflation, Import, Export, and HCI. The Inflation variable is found to have minimal if any effect on GDP per capita, thus it is removed from the equation. This is logic since it is the deflator of the GDP itself.

To overcome the inter correlation effect between Import and Export of goods and services, the difference value between them is used into a new variable in the model. Furthermore, for a more comprehensive view of the HCI indicator, data of human capital from the UN survey are combined together with the health and higher education pillars from the CGI, and the NRI skills and business usage pillars, and the World Bank data. This is done to encapsulate all its social effect and overcome the colinearity between health and education variables in different indices. Thus, a new variable "HCI_WB" is used and variables of Infant mortality, Adult literacy, and School tertiary education enrollment are removed from the model.

When applying these changes in equation (5), the new model is presented in equation (6) going from 17 down to 12 independent variables:

$$f\left(\frac{GDP}{capita}\right) = \beta_0 + (\beta_1 FTS + \beta_2 FBB + \beta_3 Intenet + \beta_4 MTS + \beta_5 MBB + \beta_6 ePart + \beta_7 TII + \beta_8 OSI) + (\beta_9 FDI + \beta_{10} Days + \beta_{11} Import_{Export}) + (\beta_{12} HCI_{WB})$$

(6)

V.4. DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF THE DATASET

In Table (2) below, the results for the descriptive statistics analysis of data sets for selected variables is presented.

¹ Software package SPSS v 23

Summary Statistics of the Dataset					
VARIABLES	#	MINIMUM	MAXIMUM	MEAN	STD. DEVIATION
GDP_Per_Capita	185	272	185,741	15,832	25,433
FDI	193	-239,337,011,214	258,390,000,000	5,315,180	35,041,441,531
Days	193	0.5	230.00	20.7	25.65
Import_Export	193	-243,227,472,757.26	638,214,000,000.00	15,581,540,606.01	54,298,051,573.47
FTS	193	0.05	112.10	16.78	16.9
MTS	193	27.41	208.50	108.65	33.333
Internet	193	1.31	99.65	60.16	30.74643271
FBB	193	0.00	51.24	13.55	14.15886434
MBB	193	0.02	168.20	52.32	42.30895608
ePart	193	0.008475	1.00	0.565482	0.280775235
TII	193	0.006600	1.00	0.415493	0.237276675
OSI	193	0.010870	1.00	0.569141	0.268049694
HCI_WB	151	0.29	0.88	0.57	0.15
EGDI	193	0.06	0.92	0.55	0.21

Table 2. Source: Calculated by authors using software package MS Excel

V.5. THE REGRESSION ANALYSIS

The correlation coefficient matrix in Table (3) below summarizes both the direction and the strength of the relationship between variables. The positive value implies the progress is in the same direction, which infers in incremental or detrimental ways. It is observed that the value of the correlation infers how the two variables are attached, the greater the bond the greater the absolute value in the matrix.

Correlation Matrix - Eq. 6													
	GDP_Per_Capita	FDI	Days	Import_Export	ePart	FTS	MTS	Internet	FBB	MBB	TII	OSI	HCI_WB
GDP_Per_Capita	1												
FDI	0.083	1											
Days	-0.223**	-0.060	1										
Import_Export	0.302**	0.567**	-0.106	1									
ePart	0.468**	0.188**	-0.272**	0.315**	1								
FTS	0.740**	0.098	-0.131	0.224**	0.591**	1							
MTS	0.274**	0.078	-0.139	0.186**	0.597**	0.446**	1						
Internet	0.411**	0.006	-0.140	0.148*	0.631**	0.504**	0.482**	1					
FBB	0.725**	0.068	-0.223**	0.281**	0.705**	0.868**	0.522**	0.627**	1				
MBB	0.574**	0.117	-0.186**	0.310**	0.553**	0.485**	0.281**	0.516**	0.669**	1			
TII	0.725**	0.087	-0.213**	0.271**	0.738**	0.793**	0.584**	0.645**	0.857**	0.581**	1		
OSI	0.498**	0.190**	-0.267**	0.322**	0.982**	0.605**	0.603**	0.625**	0.712**	0.557**	0.765**	1	
HCI_WB	0.713**	0.149	-0.264**	0.292**	0.783**	0.809**	0.559**	0.701**	0.886**	0.701**	0.919**	0.796**	1

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 3. Source: created by authors using statistical package

It is remarkable to find that the correlation matrix shows high correlation coefficient between some of the predictors. In addition to this, the VIF shows clear multi-Colinearity exist which violates the OLS assumption. Therefore, the “Factor Analysis” study as a “Dimension Reduction” method is used in order to avoid the existing multi-colinearity status without the loss of predictors.

The factor analysis results show high adequacy of data and it yields into two orthogonal factors that can explain about 70% of the variability in the predictors. The best fitted the data is conducted through KMO and test of Sphericity. Thus, equation (3) will be re-written with the new two factors as follows:

$$f\left(\frac{GDP}{Capita}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{Factor 1}) + \beta_2(\text{Factor 2}) \tag{7}$$

V.6. COEFFICIENTS^A OF FACTOR 1 & 2

Model		Standardized Coefficients
		β
1	REGR Factor score 1 for analysis 1	0.745
	REGR Factor score 2 for analysis 1	0.170

^a Dependent Variable: GDP_Per_Capita

Table 4.

Source: created by authors using statistical package

The Principal Component Analysis measures of Factor (1), with Dependent Variable as GDP_per_capita, shows that one percent increase will cause 0.745 percent point increase in economic growth. Similarly, the measures show that one percent increase in Factor (2) will cause 0.17 percent point increase in economic growth. Thus, we can infer that Factor (2) has almost ¼ effect on the GDP per Capita than that of Factor (1).

With the unstandardized coefficients calculated, the constant value is found to equal to 1,5192.446, and Factor (1) has value of 15882.094, has value of (Y) and Factor 3,589.656. Hence, we the new model is:

$$f\left(\frac{GDP}{Capita}\right) = 1,5192.446 + 15882.094(Technology) + 3,589.656(Trade)$$

(7.1)

V.7. ROTATED COMPONENT MATRIX

Using the “Rotated Factor Matrix”, below table (5) determines the exact factor loadings for each variable in the model of equation (6).

Rotated Factor Matrix shows the “Loading of coefficients”

		Component ^a	
		Factor 1	Factor 2
		1. FDI	0.012
2. Days	-0.317	-0.150	
3. Import_Export	0.206	0.845	
4. ePart	0.852	0.230	
5. FTS	0.853	0.118	
6. MTS	0.643	0.042	
7. Internet	0.800	-0.122	
8. FBB	0.924	0.109	
9. MBB	0.718	0.144	
10. TII	0.950	0.105	
11. OSI	0.861	0.238	
12. HCL_WB	0.932	0.134	

^a Rotation converged in 3 iterations.
 - Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.
 - Extraction Method Principal Component Analysis

Table 5.

Source: created by authors using statistical package

From the Principle Component Analysis above in table (5), it is clear that the “Foreign Direct Investment” and the difference between the Import and Export are highly loaded variables onto Factor #2 (Trade Factor), whereas all technology variables loads, e.g. FTS, MTS, Internet, FBB, MBB, ePart, TII, OSI, HCL_WB, are highly onto Factor 1 (Technology Factor).

Surprisingly, the predictor “Number of Days to Start a business”, although expected to load in Factor 2 (Trade factor), yet it is heavily related to “Technology Factor” with a clear inverse relationship.

V.8. MODEL SUMMARY AND EMPIRICAL RESULTS

The study is using three goodness of fit measure; these are Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin, Bartlett's test of Sphericity, and the amount of total variance explained. Below is table (5) the summary of the model^a:

Statistical summary of results				
Model	KMO	Total variance explain	R Square	ANOVA Sig.
1	0.68	68.875	0.584	0.000 ^b

^a Dependent Variable: GDP_Per_Capita

^b Predictors: (Constant), REGR factor score 2 for analysis 1, REGR factor score 1 for analysis 1

Table 6.

Source: Results calculated by authors using statistical package.

As calculated, the Root Mean Square value is almost 0.6. Data sampling adequacy, Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test is conducted. The Total variance explained has calculated output with almost 70% value, therefore the first and second values are adopted. The ANOVA test giving p value equals to NULL value, which is less than 0.05, we reject H_0 [NA] and accept H_1 . Therefore, it shows that the model with the GDP per capita we may conclude that the fitted model is statistically significant. Totally understandable, yet enlightened and quantified by this study. The final econometric model developed from the literature and the statistical analysis is presented by substituting values in equation 7.1. Its final form is:

$$f(GDP_{PerCapita}) = 1,5192.446 + 1,5882.094 [(-0.317) Days + (0.932) HCI_{WB} + (0.852) ePart + (0.853) FTS + (0.643) MTS + (0.8) Internet + (0.924) FBB + (0.718) MBB + (0.950) TII + (0.861) OSI] + 3,589.656 [(0.891) FDI + 0.845 Import_{Export}]$$

(8)

VI.FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Firstly, we accept and prove that hypothesis 1 to be true:

H_1 : *Development of e-Government portals can positively affect economic growth of countries.*

Secondly, another important finding is the Human Capital Index can encapsulate the social parameters together with the labor parameters and be represented in one comprehensive coefficient. In addition, a new finding from the PCA in the “Number of Days to start a business” variable to be counted for the Technology factor rather than the expected “Trade factor with a loading value equals (-0.317). The reflection of the amount of days needed to go through governmental process in order to establish a new business as a function of time is inversely related to offering these processes online. It is a great quantitative proof of the beneficiary of eGovernment portals and on how it can save time on businesses. Amount of time decreases with the increase of technology and accordingly reflects almost 1/3 increase in GDP_{per_Capita} .

Another significant finding is the close correlation between e-Participation and OSI. It can be explained that the more ICT infrastructure in terms of services and systems are in use, the more OSI and e-Participation values increase. Consequently, the more OSI and eParticipation, the less number of days need to start a business. From The competitiveness-based predictors used to measure the influence of eGovernment portals and to study how these affect the growth of the economic. The final framework can be visualized in figure (3).

Figure 3. Source: Developed by authors

VII.CONCLUSION

This study investigates the contextual nexus between e-Gov portals and economic growth via a macroeconomic growth model based on selected relevant competitiveness predictors. The study started with the model developed by Hai (2016) for the economic effects of e-government. Further analyses is developed to these relationships. The scope of the work is set to be cross-sectional dataset for the 193 countries of the UN survey available in year 2018. Data collected is for selected economic and e-Gov indicators. The empirical study has the GDP per capita as measurement for economic growth.

The developed econometric model is a contribution to the body of knowledge in both domains; the economic growth and the e-Gov. It detects new affirmations that all relevant variables from the competitiveness pillars can mediate the

eGovernment development composite indices together with the economic variables that are affecting growth. Findings are consistent with what the literature stated about the positive relationship between technology and growth to be true. Likewise, it provides quantitative measurements for this relationship. Besides this study provides affirmation of positive impact of eGov on growth, nevertheless it also provides a new framework that will have formed concrete bases for both academics and practitioners.

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APPENDIX A

Data collected for the 193 state members of the UN and calculated for the year 2018.

#	Variable	Data Source
1.	Inflation, annual % change	World Bank national accounts data, and OECD National Accounts data files.
2.	FDI	International Monetary Fund, Balance of Payments Statistics Yearbook and data files.
3.	No. days to start a business	World Bank, Doing Business project
4.	Imports of goods and services	World Bank national accounts data, and OECD National Accounts data files.
5.	Exports of goods and services	World Bank national accounts data, and OECD National Accounts data files.
6.	Infant mortality, deaths/1,000 live births	Estimates developed by the UN Inter-agency Group for Child Mortality Estimation (UNICEF, WHO, World Bank, UN DESA Population Division)
7.	Tertiary education enrollment, gross %	UNESCO Institute for Statistics
8.	Adult literacy rate, %	UNESCO Institute for Statistics
9.	Fixed telephone lines/100 pop	International Telecommunication Union,
10.	Mobile telephone subscriptions/100 pop	World Telecommunication/ICT Development Report and database.
11.	Individuals using Internet, %	World Telecommunication/ICT Development Report and database.
12.	Fixed broadband Internet subscriptions/100 pop	World Telecommunication/ICT Development Report and database.
13.	Mobile broadband subscriptions/100 pop	Network Readiness Index (NRI), The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), Global Competitiveness Index (GCI)
14.	GDP	World Bank national accounts data, and OECD National Accounts data files.
15.	GDP growth rate %	World Bank national accounts data, and OECD National Accounts data files.
16.	Population	United Nations Population Division. World Population Prospects: 2019 Revision. Census reports and other statistical publications from national statistical offices, Eurostat: Demographic Statistics, United Nations Statistical Division. Population and Vital Statistics Report (various years), U.S. Census Bureau: International Database, and Secretariat of the Pacific Community: Statistics and Demography Programme.
17.	EGDI	United Nations BiAnnual E-Government Survey
18.	eParticipation	United Nations BiAnnual E-Government Survey
19.	TII	United Nations BiAnnual E-Government Survey
20.	HCI	United Nations BiAnnual E-Government Survey
21.	OSI	United Nations BiAnnual E-Government Survey